

**A NOTE ON SOME RECENT RESULTS OF DA SILVA AND
SELLERS ON CONGRUENCES FOR k -REGULAR PARTITIONS
WITH DESIGNATED SUMMANDS**

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Abstract

Da Silva and Sellers proved the existence of several families containing infinitely many congruences for $PD_k(n)$ for various values of k , where $PD_k(n)$ denotes the k -regular partitions with designated summands. They also conjectured a few more congruences. In this paper, we prove their conjectural congruences, and also present some new families of congruences modulo 8 for $PD_{144k}(144n + t)$, for $t \in \{84, 132\}$ and $PD_{288k}(288n + 180)$.

1. Introduction

Andrews, Lewis and Lovejoy [1] introduced partitions with designated summands, which are constructed by taking ordinary partitions and tagging exactly one of each part size. A partition is said to be k -regular if none of its parts is divisible by k . Let $PD_k(n)$ denote the number of k -regular partitions of n with designated summands. The generating function of $PD_k(n)$ is given by [1, Corollary 3]

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_k(n)q^n = \frac{f_6 f_k f_{2k} f_{3k}}{f_1 f_2 f_3 f_{6k}}, \quad (1)$$

where for $k \geq 1$,

$$f_k := (q^k; q^k)_{\infty} = \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - q^{kn}), \quad |q| < 1.$$

Recently, da Silva and Sellers [2] proved several families containing infinitely many congruences for $PD_k(n)$ for various values of k . In particular, for all $n \geq 0$

and $k \geq 1$,

$$PD_{6k}(6n + 4) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \tag{2}$$

$$PD_{12k}(12n + 9) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \tag{3}$$

$$PD_{12k}(12n + 10) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{4}$$

They also conjectured the following congruences. For $k \geq 1$ and $n \geq 0$,

$$PD_{12k-4}(6n) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \tag{5}$$

$$PD_{16k}(16n + 12) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{6}$$

$$PD_{18k}(18n + 12) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{7}$$

In Section 2, we prove the above congruences.

In Section 3 of this note, we prove the following new theorem.

Theorem 1.1 *For $k \geq 1$ and $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$PD_{144k}(144n + 84) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{8}$$

$$PD_{144k}(144n + 132) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \tag{9}$$

$$PD_{288k}(288n + 180) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{10}$$

We now recall from [2] and [3] some well-known 2- and 3-dissection formulas.

Lemma 1.2 *We have*

$$\frac{1}{f_1^2} = \frac{f_8^5}{f_2^5 f_{16}^2} + 2q \frac{f_4^2 f_{16}^2}{f_2^5 f_8}, \tag{11}$$

$$\frac{1}{f_1^4} = \frac{f_4^{14}}{f_2^{14} f_8^4} + 4q \frac{f_4^2 f_8^4}{f_2^{10}}, \tag{12}$$

$$f_1 f_3 = \frac{f_2 f_8^2 f_{12}^4}{f_4^2 f_6 f_{24}^2} - q \frac{f_4^4 f_6 f_{24}^2}{f_2 f_8^2 f_{12}^2}, \tag{13}$$

$$\frac{1}{f_1 f_3} = \frac{f_8^2 f_{12}^5}{f_2^2 f_4 f_6^4 f_{24}^2} + q \frac{f_4^5 f_{24}^2}{f_2^4 f_6^2 f_8^2 f_{12}^2}, \tag{14}$$

$$\frac{f_3}{f_1^3} = \frac{f_4^6 f_6^3}{f_2^9 f_{12}^2} + 3q \frac{f_4^2 f_6 f_{12}^2}{f_2^7}, \tag{15}$$

$$\frac{f_3^2}{f_1^2} = \frac{f_4^4 f_6 f_{12}^2}{f_2^5 f_8 f_{24}} + 2q \frac{f_4 f_6^2 f_8 f_{24}}{f_2^4 f_{12}}, \tag{16}$$

$$\frac{f_1^2}{f_2} = \frac{f_9^2}{f_{18}} - 2q \frac{f_3 f_{18}^2}{f_6 f_9}, \tag{17}$$

$$\frac{f_2^2}{f_1} = \frac{f_6 f_9^2}{f_3 f_{18}} + q \frac{f_{18}^2}{f_9}, \tag{18}$$

$$f_1 f_2 = \frac{f_6 f_9^4}{f_3 f_{18}^2} - q f_9 f_{18} - 2q^2 \frac{f_3 f_{18}^4}{f_6 f_9^2}, \tag{19}$$

$$\frac{1}{f_1 f_2} = \frac{f_9^9}{f_3^6 f_6^2 f_{18}^3} + q \frac{f_9^6}{f_3^5 f_6^3} + 3q^2 \frac{f_9^3 f_{18}^3}{f_3^4 f_6^4} - 2q^3 \frac{f_{18}^6}{f_3^3 f_6^5} + 4q^4 \frac{f_{18}^9}{f_3^2 f_6^6 f_9^3}. \tag{20}$$

We end this section by noting the following congruences which can be easily established:

$$\begin{aligned} f_1^2 &\equiv f_2 \pmod{2}, \\ f_1^4 &\equiv f_2^2 \pmod{4}, \\ f_1^8 &\equiv f_2^4 \pmod{8}. \end{aligned}$$

We will frequently use the identities in Lemma 1.2 and the above congruences in the subsequent sections, quite often without referring to these.

2. Proofs of (5) – (7)

From (1) and (14), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{12k-4}(n)q^n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{4m}(n)q^n \\ &= \frac{f_{4m}f_{8m}f_{12m}f_6}{f_2f_{24m}} \cdot \frac{1}{f_1f_3} \\ &= \frac{f_{4m}f_{8m}f_{12m}f_6}{f_{24m}f_2} \left(\frac{f_8^2f_{12}^5}{f_2^2f_4f_6^4f_{24}^2} + q \frac{f_4^5f_{24}^2}{f_2^4f_6^2f_8^2f_{12}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $m = 3k - 1$. Extracting the even terms of the above, and then employing (18) and (19), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{12k-4}(2n)q^n &= \frac{f_{2m}f_{4m}f_{6m}f_3}{f_{12m}f_1} \cdot \frac{f_4^2f_6^5}{f_1^2f_2f_3^4f_{12}^2} \\ &\equiv \frac{f_{6m}}{f_3f_{12m}} \cdot \frac{f_2^2}{f_1} \cdot f_{2m}f_{4m} \\ &\equiv \frac{f_{6m}}{f_3f_{12m}} \left(\frac{f_6f_9^2}{f_3f_{18}} + q \frac{f_{18}^2}{f_9} \right) \left(\frac{f_{12m}f_{18m}^4}{f_{6m}f_{36m}^2} - q^{2m}f_{18m}f_{36m} - 2q^{4m} \frac{f_{6m}f_{36m}^4}{f_{12m}f_{18m}^2} \right) \pmod{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{3n} from both sides of the above, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{12k-4}(6n)q^n &\equiv \frac{f_{2m}}{f_1f_{4m}} \cdot \frac{f_2f_3^2}{f_1f_6} \cdot \frac{f_{4m}f_{6m}^4}{f_{2m}f_{12m}^2} \\ &\equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Equating the coefficients of q^n from both sides of the above, we arrive at (5).

Next, we prove (6).

From (1) and (14), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{16k}(n)q^n &= \frac{f_6 f_{16k} f_{32k} f_{48k}}{f_2 f_{96k}} \cdot \frac{1}{f_1 f_3} \\ &= \frac{f_6 f_{16k} f_{32k} f_{48k}}{f_2 f_{96k}} \left(\frac{f_8^2 f_{12}^5}{f_2^2 f_4 f_6^4 f_{24}^2} + q \frac{f_4^5 f_{24}^2}{f_2^4 f_6^2 f_8^2 f_{12}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{2n} from both sides and then using (12) and (15), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{16k}(2n)q^n &= \frac{f_4^2 f_6^5 f_{8k} f_{16k} f_{24k}}{f_2 f_{12}^2 f_{48k}} \cdot \frac{f_3}{f_1^3} \cdot \frac{1}{f_3^4} \\ &= \frac{f_4^2 f_6^5 f_{8k} f_{16k} f_{24k}}{f_2 f_{12}^2 f_{48k}} \left(\frac{f_4^6 f_6^3}{f_2^9 f_{12}^2} + 3q \frac{f_4^2 f_6 f_{12}^2}{f_2^7} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{f_{14}^{14}}{f_6^{14} f_{24}^4} + 4q^3 \frac{f_{12}^2 f_{24}^4}{f_6^{10}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{2n} from both sides of the above, we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{16k}(4n)q^n = \frac{f_{4k} f_{8k} f_{12k}}{f_{24k}} \left(\frac{f_2^8 f_6^{10}}{f_1^{10} f_3^6 f_{12}^4} + 12q^2 \frac{f_2^4 f_6^2 f_{12}^4}{f_1^8 f_3^4} \right).$$

Therefore, using (16), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{16k}(4n)q^n &\equiv \frac{f_{4k} f_{8k} f_{12k}}{f_{24k}} \left(\frac{f_2^4}{f_6^2} \cdot \frac{f_3^2}{f_1^2} + 4q^2 f_{12}^2 \right) \\ &\equiv \frac{f_{4k} f_{8k} f_{12k}}{f_{24k}} \left(\frac{f_2^4}{f_6^2} \left(\frac{f_4^4 f_6 f_{12}^2}{f_2^5 f_8 f_{24}} + 2q \frac{f_4 f_6^2 f_8 f_{24}}{f_2^4 f_{12}} \right) + 4q^2 f_{12}^2 \right) \pmod{8}. \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{2n+1} from both sides, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{16k}(8n+4)q^n &\equiv 2 \frac{f_{2k} f_{4k} f_{6k}}{f_{12k}} \cdot \frac{f_1^4 f_3^6}{f_6^4} \cdot \frac{f_2 f_3^2 f_4 f_{12}}{f_1^4 f_6} \\ &\equiv 2 \frac{f_2 f_4 f_{12} f_{2k} f_{4k} f_{6k}}{f_6 f_{12k}} \pmod{8}, \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

from which it readily follows that

$$PD_{16k}(16n+12) \equiv 0 \pmod{8},$$

which is (6).

Now we prove (7). To that end, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{18k}(n)q^n &= \frac{f_6 f_{18k} f_{36k} f_{54k}}{f_3 f_{108k}} \cdot \frac{1}{f_1 f_2} \\ &= \frac{f_6 f_{18k} f_{36k} f_{54k}}{f_3 f_{108k}} \left(\frac{f_9^9}{f_3^9 f_6^2 f_{18}^3} + q \frac{f_9^6}{f_3^5 f_6^3} + 3q^2 \frac{f_9^3 f_{18}^3}{f_3^4 f_6^4} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 2q^3 \frac{f_{18}^6}{f_3^3 f_6^5} + 4q^4 \frac{f_{18}^9}{f_3^2 f_6^6 f_9^3} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{3n} from both sides of the above, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{18k}(3n)q^n &= \frac{f_{6k}f_{12k}f_{18k}}{f_{36k}} \left(\frac{f_3^9}{f_1^7 f_2 f_6^3} - 2q \frac{f_6^6}{f_1^4 f_2^4} \right) \\ &\equiv \frac{f_6 f_{6k} f_{12k} f_{18k}}{f_2^5 f_{36k}} \cdot f_1 f_3 - 2q \frac{f_6^6 f_{6k} f_{12k} f_{18k}}{f_2^6 f_{36k}} \\ &\equiv 6q \frac{f_6^6 f_{6k} f_{12k} f_{18k}}{f_2^6 f_{36k}} + \frac{f_6 f_{6k} f_{12k} f_{18k}}{f_2^5 f_{36k}} \cdot \left(\frac{f_2 f_8^2 f_{12}^4}{f_4^2 f_6 f_{24}^2} - q \frac{f_4^4 f_6 f_{24}^2}{f_2 f_8^2 f_{12}^2} \right) \pmod{8}. \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{2n} , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{18k}(6n)q^n &\equiv \frac{f_{3k} f_{6k} f_{9k}}{f_1^4 f_{18k}} \cdot \frac{f_4^2 f_6^4}{f_2^2 f_{12}^2} \\ &\equiv \frac{f_6^4 f_{3k} f_{6k} f_{9k}}{f_{12}^2 f_{18k}} \cdot \frac{f_1^4}{f_2^2} \cdot \frac{f_2}{f_4^2} \\ &\equiv \frac{f_6^4 f_{3k} f_{6k} f_{9k}}{f_{12}^2 f_{18k}} \left(\frac{f_9^2}{f_{18}} - 2q \frac{f_3 f_{18}^2}{f_6 f_9} \right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{f_{18}^2}{f_{36}} - 2q^2 \frac{f_6 f_{36}^2}{f_{12} f_{18}} \right)^2 \pmod{8}. \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{3n+2} from both sides of the above, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{18k}(18n + 12)q^n &\equiv 4 \frac{f_2^4 f_k f_{2k} f_{3k}}{f_4^2 f_{6k}} \left(\frac{f_1^2 f_6^8}{f_2^2 f_3^2 f_{12}^2} - \frac{f_2 f_3^4 f_{12}}{f_4 f_6} \right) \\ &\equiv 4 \frac{f_k f_{2k} f_{3k}}{f_{6k}} \left(\frac{f_6^3 f_{12}}{f_2} - \frac{f_6^3 f_{12}}{f_2} \right) \\ &\equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that $PD_{18k}(18n + 12) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$. This completes the proof of (7).

3. Proof of Theorem 1.1

We have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{144k}(n) = \frac{f_{144k} f_{288k} f_{432k} f_6}{f_{864k} f_1 f_2 f_3}.$$

Proceeding as in the proof of (6) in the previous section up to (21), we find that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{144k}(8n + 4)q^n \equiv 2 \frac{f_{18k} f_{36k} f_{54k}}{f_{108k}} \frac{f_2 f_4 f_{12}}{f_6} \pmod{8}.$$

We extract

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{144k}(16n + 4)q^n &\equiv 2 \frac{f_6 f_{9k} f_{18k} f_{27k}}{f_3 f_{54k}} \cdot f_1 f_2 \\ &\equiv 2 \frac{f_6 f_{9k} f_{18k} f_{27k}}{f_3 f_{54k}} \left(\frac{f_6 f_9^4}{f_3 f_{18}^2} - q f_9 f_{18} - 2q^2 \frac{f_3 f_{18}^4}{f_6 f_9^2} \right) \pmod{8}. \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{3n+2} from both sides of the above, we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{144k}(48n + 36)q^n \equiv 4 \frac{f_6^4 f_{3k} f_{6k} f_{9k}}{f_3^2 f_{18k}} \pmod{8}, \tag{22}$$

from which it readily follows that

$$\begin{aligned} PD_{144k}(144n + 84) &\equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \\ PD_{144k}(144n + 132) &\equiv 0 \pmod{8}, \end{aligned}$$

which are (8) and (9), respectively.

Next, the generating function representation for $PD_{288k}(n)$ and (22) imply that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{288k}(48n + 36)q^n \equiv 4 \frac{f_6^4 f_{6k} f_{12k} f_{18k}}{f_3^2 f_{36k}} \pmod{8}.$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{3n} from both sides of the above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} PD_{288k}(144n + 36)q^n &\equiv 4 \frac{f_2^4 f_{2k} f_{4k} f_{6k}}{f_{12k}} \cdot \frac{1}{f_1^2} \\ &\equiv 4 \frac{f_2^4 f_{2k} f_{4k} f_{6k}}{f_{12k}} \left(\frac{f_8^5}{f_2^5 f_{16}^2} + 2q \frac{f_4^2 f_{16}^2}{f_2^5 f_8} \right) \pmod{8}, \end{aligned}$$

from which we arrive at $PD_{288k}(288n + 180) \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$ to complete the proof.

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